

Frequency Of Vitamin K Deficiency In Newborn Presenting With Bleeding

Nazia Mumtaz, Ikram din Ujjan, Sadia Akbar, Sana Fatema, Kiran Aamir, Aamir Ramzan

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 19, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: November 30, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Vitamin K Deficiency Bleeding, Hemorrhagic Disease of Newborn, Coagulation factors</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5759956</p>	<p>OBJECTIVE: To determine the frequency of vitamin K deficiency in newborns presenting with bleeding.</p> <p>STUDY DESIGN: Cross sectional study</p> <p>DURATION AND PLACE OF STUDY: This study was conducted at the department of Pathology and the department of Pediatrics LUMHS from September 2019 till December 2020.</p> <p>METHODOLOGY: This study consisted of 114 patients presenting with bleeding admitted through the outpatient department, as well as from Paediatrics department of Liaquat University Hospital Hyderabad. Detailed history of bleeding and clinical examination of the patient was done. All patients underwent for base line and specific investigations. All samples were analyzed for Vitamin K levels. All data was entered in a specified proforma designed for this purpose. Inclusion criteria were that newborns and neonates from both genders age from day 01 up to 6 months who presented with bleeding from any site including intracranial, skin, gastrointestinal and bleeding from injection site.</p> <p>Exclusion criteria included those patients who had any coagulopathies, acute leukemia, infants of mothers who were on anticonvulsants, warfarin, or antituberculous therapy, who had any recent Blood transfusion or those who had platelet counts less than 100. Results were prepared with help of tables and graphs. Data was analyzed through SPSS software version 20.</p> <p>RESULTS: Total 114 patients were included in this study. There was age ranging from 01 to 180 days (upto 06 months). (The mean age was 44.01 days.) Median age was 08 days. 69.3% were delivered through Normal vaginal delivery whereas 30.7% through a Caesarian section. 66.7% were delivered at Term while 33.3% were born Preterm. 36.8% were found to have Vitamin K deficiency whereas 63.2 % had normal levels. Umbilical stump bleeding, Skin/ mucosal bleed & Genitourinary bleeds were the commonest sites of bleeding followed by skin/ bruises/ injection sites, nose bleeding. PT and APTT were prolonged in almost all the cases.</p> <p>Conclusion: Vitamin K deficiency causing hemorrhagic disease of the newborn is a common problem in neonates. It shows a dramatic response to vitamin K injection. It is more common in male, preterm and low birth weight babies.</p>

Introduction

Haemorrhagic Disease of Newborn (HDN), also called vitamin K deficiency bleeding (VKDB), The name change from HDN to vitamin K deficiency bleeding (VKDB) was recommended by the ISTH Pediatric/ Perinatal Subcommittee in 1999 to clarify that the etiological basis was solely due to VK-deficiency is the occurrence of spontaneous bleeding in early days of life.¹

Vitamin K is essential for the γ -carboxylation of glutamic acid residues of coagulant factors II, VII, IX and X. Deficiency of vitamin K leads to inadequate activity of these factors, resulting in bleeding. The classical role of VK is as an anti-haemorrhagic factor that is needed for the synthesis in the liver of functional forms of prothrombin (factor II) together with factors VII, IX and X.²

After secretion into the blood, these four VK-dependent proteins become available to take part in blood coagulation, the complex series of events that, once initiated, culminates in the conversion of fibrinogen to fibrin and the formation of a haemostatic plug.³ The biochemical role of VK is to act as a cofactor for the conversion of specific peptide-bound glutamate (Glu) residues to γ carboxyglutamate (Gla) residues.⁴

Vitamin K-dependent carboxylation is a posttranslational modification that converts specific glutamate (Glu) residues to γ carboxyglutamate (Gla) residues in vitamin K-dependent proteins. Hence VK-dependent proteins are often known as Gla-proteins. Two other Gla-proteins, proteins C and S, have well-defined roles in the negative feedback control of coagulation.⁵ As opposed to adults, neonates have reduced stores of vitamin K at birth owing to insufficient placental transfer. This is compounded by deficient vitamin K content in breast milk

resulting in higher levels of proteins induced in the absence of vitamin K in breastfed neonates.⁶ Bleeding can occur from birth upto six months of life.⁷

Haemorrhagic disease of newborn is more prevalent in specific group of babies like breast-fed infants, preterm babies, malabsorption, cystic fibrosis and neonatal cholestasis etc. Cases of VKDB are conventionally divided into three groups according to age at onset of bleeding: “early” (onset within 24 h of birth), “classical” (onset 1–7 full days after birth) and “late” (onset after 7 days).⁽⁸⁾ Classic VKDB develops from 24 hours after birth up to 1 week, most commonly on day 2. Late VKDB occurs on or after day 8 most often between 2 and 12 weeks of age.⁷ The incidence of late VKDB ranges from 4.4 to 7.2 per 100,000 births.⁹

In addition to reflecting the absence of standardization for case definitions there is evidence that the frequency of VKDB reflects economic and nutritional status, community practices such as male circumcision, and probably genetic variations such as those known to affect the metabolism and recycling of Vitamin K.

While relatively exceptional, the bleeding is characteristically severe, with intracranial hemorrhages occurring in 30% to 80% of cases. Bleeding can also occur from the nose, skin (petechiae, bruising, venipuncture sites), umbilicus, urogenital tract, gastrointestinal tract, or intrathoracically.¹

The etiology of late Vitamin K deficiency bleeding is complex. Limited placental Vitamin K transfer, low Vitamin K content in breast milk, rapid Vitamin K excretion, an immature Vitamin K cycle, liver stores dominated by K1 rather than K2, gut bacteria that do not contribute to Vitamin K status, a slow rise of clotting factors until about 90 days after birth, and the possibility of pathologic contributors such as hepatobiliary or mal-absorptive disease all contribute to an infant’s risk for late VKDB.²

Adults and infants have important differences in their liver storage of VK. In adults, liver storage is 10% phylloquinone (K1) and 90% menaquinone (K2). In infants, liver storage is overall more limited, and phylloquinone predominates over menaquinone. Hepatobiliary and malabsorptive diseases are a main cause of late VKDB and can often result in the failure of oral VK prophylaxis, and though less common, can also result in the failure of IM VK prophylaxis.¹⁰ Mothers who have been taking anti-coagulants, anti-convulsants, cephalosporins, VK antagonists such as warfarin, or tuberculostatic agents during pregnancy will have a newborn requiring immediate IM VK prophylaxis due to the high risk of developing VKDB in the first 24 hours of life.¹¹

The Adequate Intake for vitamin K is set at 2 mcg/day for infants 0 to 6 months of age. Human breast milk contains relatively low concentrations of vitamin K1 and K2, with average concentrations of 0.25 mcg/dL to 0.5 mcg/dL, IM and oral VK are equally effective in preventing classic VKDB, but Intramuscular injection of VK is more effective than oral VK at preventing late VKDB,¹² which might be due to inconsistent administration and the possibility of hepatobiliary or malabsorptive disorders.

Implications of any uncontrolled bleed in the infant include anemia, ischemia, shock, brain injury, disseminated intravascular coagulation, and death. Intracranial hemorrhage is a frequent manifestation of vitamin K deficiency (VKD) in infancy. It is the presenting symptom in approximately 50% of cases with late vitamin K deficiency bleeding (VKDB) in Western Europe, with even higher rates (up to 82%) reported in developing countries.¹³

The efficacy of vitamin K prophylactic regimens is evaluated on the basis of the incidence of VKDB under a given regimen. The incidence is calculated from the number of ascertained cases from general surveillance studies. Random variations in factors strongly associated with VKDB—particularly the rate of breastfeeding and the incidence of cholestasis—may have a significant impact on the incidence.¹⁴

METHODOLOGY:

Inclusion Criteria

- Age : day 01 up to 6 months
- Both genders
- Presenting with: intracranial bleeding, Skin bleeding, Gastrointestinal bleeding, Bleeding from injection site.

Exclusion Criteria

- Coagulopathies
- Acute leukemia
- Mothers on anticonvulsants, warfarin, antituberculous therapy
- Recent Blood transfusion
- Thrombocytopenia: platelet counts < 100

DATA COLLECTION

The study was performed after approval of the study by REC of CPSP. A written informed consent for the study and procedure was obtained from the patient or next of kin. Patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria at Pathology Department of Liaquat University Hospital Hyderabad were selected after taking detailed history and clinical examination. After all aseptic measures 5 ml of venous blood was drawn by using a disposable syringe and was divided into two test tubes and following investigations were performed:

- Complete Blood Count for Hemoglobin level and Platelet count was performed on System XN1000i from Japan
- PT and APTT was performed on Coagulation Analyzer CA- 600
- Vitamin K level was measured by ELISA

Vitamin K1 (VK1) ELISA Kit

Range: 0.16 ng/ml - 10 ng/ml

Sensitivity: 0.09 ng/ml

Storage: Store the 96-well plate, Standards, HRP-conjugate reagent and Biotin-conjugated antibody at -20°C, and the rest of the kit components at 4°C. Application: For quantitative detection of VK1 in Serum, Plasma and other biological fluids.

Principle of the Assay

This kit is based on a competitive enzyme-linked immuno-sorbent assay technology. VK1 is pre-coated onto a 96-well plate. The standards, samples and a biotin conjugated antibody specific to VK1 are added to the wells and incubated. After washing away the unbound conjugates, avidin conjugated to Horseradish Peroxidase is added to each microplate well. After TMB substrate solution is added only wells that contain VK1 will produce a blue colour product that changes into yellow after adding the stop solution.

The intensity of the yellow colour is inversely proportional to the VK1 amount bound on the plate. The O.D. absorbance is measured spectrophotometrically at 450 nm in a microplate reader, and then the concentration of VK1 can be calculated.

DATA ANALYSIS

Data was analyzed using SPSS (statistical package for social sciences) version 20. Mean and standard deviation was calculated for quantitative variables like; age, vitamin K level, PT, APTT. Frequency and percentages were computed for qualitative

variables like; gender, bleeding pattern, mode of delivery, term or preterm birth and Vitamin K deficiency.

Effect modifiers; age and gender were controlled by stratification of data using Chi-square test. Significance level was kept at a p value of < 0.05.

RESULTS:

After collection of all the samples with regards to the inclusion and exclusion criteria, for each patient, the variables were recorded on the proforma. The values obtained were then analyzed on SPSS version 20. Total sample size was n = 114 patients which were of age ranging from day 01 upto day 180 (upto 06months). Out of 114, 56 were males and 58 were females. P- value: 0.03. Male to female ratio was found to be M: F = 1.6:1. 38 Were delivered as preterm babies and as 76 full term. P-value: 0.013 (Table 1)

79 (69.3) Delivered through normal delivery whereas 35 (30.7) were delivered through a caesarean section. PT, a PTT, were prolonged in almost all of the cases. Mean PT was recorded as 21.14 and mean aPTT was 51.84. Out of 114 patients, 63.2% had normal vitamin K level whereas 36.8% were found to have low Vitamin K level. (<0.16 ng/ml) Vitamin K level: Mean value was found to be **0.914 ng/ml ± 1.93**

Table 1: PATIENT DISTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO PRETERM/ TERM BIRTH

Birth	Low	Normal	Total
Term	22	54	76
Preterm	20	18	38
Total	42	72	114

(P-VALUE: 0.013)

Table 2: FREQUENCY OF VKDB ACCORDING TO TYPE

Type	Frequency	Percentage %
Early (<24 hrs)	4	3.5
Classical (day1 to day 7) 1st weel of life	19	16.7
Late (day 8 upto 180 days) 6 months of age	19	16.7
other causes of bleeding	72	63.2
Total	114	100

Table 3: AGE BASED DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS

Age (in days)	Frequency	Percent
1	8	7
2	9	7.9
3	13	11.4
4	8	7
5	8	7
6	4	3.5
7	5	4.4
8	3	2.6

9	2	1.8
10	2	1.8
11	2	1.8
12	1	0.9
13	2	1.8
14	1	0.9
15	1	0.9
18	1	0.9
25	1	0.9
27	1	0.9
30	2	1.8
33	2	1.8
46	1	0.9
60	5	4.4
75	4	3.5
87	2	1.8
90	3	2.6
120	6	5.3
135	2	1.8

147	2	1.8
150	8	7
180	5	4.4
Total	114	100

Table 4: FREQUENCY OF SITE OF BLEEDING

SITE OF BLEEDING	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL
Umbilical	12	15	27
BRUISES/ SKIN	17	12	29
GIT	12	8	20
Urinary tract/ Heamturia	6	8	14
NOSE/ MOUTH	4	8	12
Multiple sites	5	7	12
Total	56	58	114

Fig 1:Site of bleeding

DISCUSSION

Vitamin K deficiency bleeding is one of the most common causes of acquired haemostatic disorder in early infancy. The neonatal hemostatic system is constantly under development with quickly fluctuating concentrations of several coagulation proteins. Thus, determining the etiology of bleeding in a newborn has further challenges beyond those seen in older children or adults.¹⁶ Bleeding can be seen in both well and sick newborns due to congenital causes, such as hemophilia or von Willebrand disease, and acquired causes, such as liver failure or disseminated intravascular coagulation.⁵

The method used in present study is a direct measurement of vitamin K concentration by photo spectrometrical assay (ELISA). that has not been used previously in any local study of Pakistan. Other studies have used PIVKA (Protein Induced in Vitamin K Absence) to assess the deficiency, which is not a specific indicator.¹⁷ The vast majority of previous studies demonstrated that this disease is more frequent in boys than girls.¹⁸ The present study showed a M:F ratio of 1.6 : 1 which was a similar ratio to that in the other studies on VK deficiency.¹⁹ A survey conducted in Japan by Takahashi et al. reports that in 63 (88.7%) observed cases of late VKDB, vitamin K had been administered orally at least once during the first month of life, so we could speculate that the oral route could be not effective in preventing late episodes; alternatively, higher dosages or more administrations may be required.²⁴

Fifty patients having haemorrhagic disease of newborn were studied. Out of whom 34 babies (68%) were males and 16 (32%) were females ($p=0.047$). Thirty six (72%) babies were of late onset disease ($p=0.094$). Mean age at presentation of late onset disease was 2.36 ± 0.96 months with range of 1-4 months.⁴⁸ Twelve (24%) babies were of classic onset disease and mean age at presentation was 2.75 ± 1.14 days. Two (4%) babies were of early onset disease. Overall mean age at onset of symptoms was 51.65 ± 39.49 days.²⁶

In our study, Mean age was 44.01 ± 57.804 , Median age was 8.00, Range was 179. Early VKDB was found in 4 (3.5%)²⁷ whereas Classical VKDB was observed in 19 (16.7%). Late VKDB was also observed in 19 (16.7%) of patients. The remaining patients presented with bleeding due to causes other than vitamin k deficiency were 72 (63.2%).²⁸ Another study shows Forty two (84%) babies delivered by spontaneous vaginal delivery while 8 (16%) by caesarean section ($p=0.020$).²⁹ Twenty eight babies were born by normal vaginal delivery and seven by cesarean section.⁵⁰ Thirty (60%) babies were delivered at homes, 13 (26%) babies at private clinics and 7 (14%) at government hospitals ($p=0.025$).

Eby CS et al. PJMS, march. 2008, showed following results about bleeding sites percentage. (Total=35) Skin Bruises 25 (71%), Intracranial 4 (11.4 %), Rectal bleeding 12 (34%), Blood in stool 17 (48 %), Nasal bleeding 14 (40 %), Injection site 7 (20 %), Blood in urine 1 (2%).²⁹ The common bleeding sites in our study was found to be umbilical cord bleeding in 27 (23.7%), bruises/ skin bleeding in 29(25.4%), gastrointestinal 20(17.5%), genitourinary bleeding in 14(12.3%), epistaxis/ mouth bleeding in 12(10.5%), Bleeding from multiple sites was observed in 12(10.5%).³⁰

A study conducted in Albania reported Seven infants presenting with ICH due to late VKDB. All infants were born in hospital at term, meaning that prophylaxis with vitamin K 1 mg i.m was administered in the first hour

of life. The mean age at presentation was 41.8 ± 4.9 days. All cases were born at term.³¹ Whereas in our study, only one patient had suspected intracranial bleed, along with bleeding from multiple sites; nose, genitourinary. Vitamin K deficiency can also occur due to secondary reasons. For instance, chronic diarrhoea, celiac disease, biliary atresia, cystic fibrosis, alpha 1-antitrypsin deficiency, abetalipoproteinemia and a history of maternal warfarin usage for a long period may induce vitamin K deficiency. Newborns only have 20-50% levels of adult coagulation activity. Lack of vitamin K administration at birth, diarrhoea, and prolonged use of antibiotics make them prone to bleeding associated with vitamin K deficiency.³² It is therefore essential to evaluate the frequency causes of vitamin K deficiency in our local population in order to avoid fatal morbidity and mortality among newborns.³¹

CONCLUSION

We have reviewed the reasons behind the bleeding in newborns and infants in order to assess the burden of vitamin k deficiency in our population. This study will aid in reducing the rate of devastating complications that occur as a result of late vitamin K deficiency bleeding leading to fatal intracranial haemorrhage. Vitamin K deficiency bleeding (VKDB) in infancy is a serious but preventable cause of mortality or permanent disability. Lack of epidemiologic data for VKDB in population of Sindh, hinders development and implementation of effective prevention strategies

Univocal recommendations about vitamin K prophylaxis are not available. We usually follow the guidelines of other European countries, which may not be appropriate for our setup due to a different genetic makeup of our population. Though the oral route may be suitable for healthy not-preterm newborn infants, but we must remember that many pathological conditions affecting the absorption of lipid soluble vitamins or causing bleeding are not clearly identifiable at birth. Prophylaxis is needed even for healthy newborns without risk factors for bleeding.

Other forms of vitamin K supplementation, including oral administration of Food and Drug Administration-approved vitamin K preparations and maternal supplements during pregnancy or lactation, do not have the same effectiveness as the parenteral form. An inter professional approach to education can be effective in increasing acceptance of vitamin K prophylaxis and decreasing the incidence of vitamin K deficiency bleeding. This study will provide a positive approach to highlight common misconceptions about vitamin K prophylaxis and clinical collaboration to prevent vitamin K deficiency bleeding.

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Author Information

Dr Nazia Mumtaz

Lecturer In Pathology Department Lumhs Jamshoro

Professor Dr Ikram din Ujjan

Vice Chancellor, Lumhs, Jamshoro

Dr Sadia Akbar

Lecturer In Pathology Department Lumhs Jamshoro

Dr Sana Fatema

Lecturer In Pathology Department, Lumhs Jamshoro

Dr Kiran Aamir

Assistant Professor In Pathology Department Lumhs Jamshoro

Dr Aamir Ramzan

Lecturer In Pathology Department Lumhs Jamshoro